

NUMERICAL MODELING FOR MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF Namd™ CFRP

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Introduction

SEM image of conventional Carbon fiber.

+ Carbon Nano Tube (CNT)

SEM image of Namd™ Carbon Fiber.

- Namd™ CFRP (CFRP containing CNT) was developed by NITTA CORPORATION.
- The CNTs are uniformly coated on carbon fibers and form a network layer.
- The same manufacturing method as conventional CFRP prepreg can be applied to Namd™ CFRP prepreg.

Specimen	Interfacial toughness (%)	Log damping ratio	Elastic modulus change rate (0.1→1000 mm/s) (%)
Namd™ CFRP	130	0.0841 (115%)	2
CFRP	100	0.0732 (100%)	10

Toughness Experiment

Interlaminar toughness of Namd™ CFRP laminates is about 30% greater than that of conventional CFRP laminates.

Vibration Experiment

Specimen

15 × 200 × t 2 mm
0° laminates (longitudinal reinforcement)

Result

Damping ratio of Namd™ CFRP is greater than that of conventional CFRP.

Three-point bending Experiment

Specimen

15 × 100 × t 2 mm
0° laminates (longitudinal reinforcement)

Result

Speed dependency of Namd™ CFRP is smaller than that of conventional CFRP.

Impact Experiment

Experimental condition

- Impactor was dropped from a height of 350 mm.
- Weight of impactor is 450 g.
- Impactor was made from SUS304 stainless steel.

Results of ultrasonic flaw detection test

Namd™ CFRP

Conventional CFRP

Small ← Delamination → Large

Namd™ CFRP laminates have less delamination than conventional CFRP laminates.

Impact Analysis

Analysis model

- Analysis condition is equal to experiment.
- Impactor speed is 2.62 m/s. Kinetic energy is equal to that of experiment.

- We introduced cohesive contact with mixed-mode traction-separation law to ply-ply interface in order to express delamination.

Result of impact analysis

Namd™ CFRP

- Red areas express delamination.
- White areas express crack.

Conventional CFRP

Crack of Namd™ CFRP laminates is similar to conventional CFRP laminates.

Namd™ CFRP laminates have less delamination than conventional CFRP laminates.

Conclusion

- The mechanical properties of Namd™ CFRP and conventional CFRP were compared by conducting various experiments.
- We conducted impact analysis, and research amount of crack and delamination of each laminate. From impact analysis, we think that CNT layer of Namd™ CFRP strengthen layer-layer interface.